
Research Article

Nomenclatural novelties in *Allium* (Amaryllidaceae, Allioideae)

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Abstract: A replacement name, *Allium sichuanense* R.Kr.Singh, is proposed for the illegitimate *A. stoloniferum* D.F.Xie, R.Y.Cheng & X.J.He, which is a later homonym of *A. stoloniferum* Ownbey & T.D.Jacobsen. In addition, *Nectaroscordum cigdemiae* Yild. is transferred to *Allium* L. as *A. cigdemiae* (Yild.) R.Kr.Singh, based on its morphological affinity with other species of *Allium*.

Keywords: *Allium stoloniferum*, China, Illegitimate, Later homonym, *Nectaroscordum cigdemiae*, Sichuan Province, Turkey

Introduction

The genus *Allium* L. comprises around 1090 species worldwide (POWO, 2025). In China, about 143 species are recorded so far, of which nearly 55 are endemic (Cheng et al., 2025; POWO, 2025). The name *A. stoloniferum* D.F.Xie, R.Y.Cheng & X.J.He is illegitimate because it is a later homonym of *A. stoloniferum* Ownbey & T.D.Jacobsen, in accordance with Article 53.1 of the International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Turland et al., 2018). To resolve this nomenclatural issue, the replacement name *A. sichuanense* R.Kr.Singh is proposed herein.

In Turkey, *Allium* is represented by about 240 species, with nearby 90 endemics (POWO, 2025). The genus *Nectaroscordum* Lindl. is currently treated as a synonym of *Allium* L. Therefore, *Nectaroscordum cigdemiae* Yild., described from Turkey by Yıldırım (2012), is here transferred to *Allium* as *A. cigdemiae* (Yild.) R.Kr.Singh.

Nomenclature

Allium cigdemiae (Yild.) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Nectaroscordum cigdemiae* Yıld., Ot Sist. Bot. Dergisi 19(1): 6. 2012.

Holotype: Turkey, B1 Balıkesir, Edremit, Zeytinli, Kazdağı, Ayı deresi çevresi, kuz, koyu gölgeli ve aşırı nemli orman, 600 m, 27 May 1991, Ş. Yıldırım (Herbarium of Yıldırım); isotypes Herbarium of Yıldırım, EGE, GAZI, HUB.

Distribution: Endemic to Turkey (Türkiye).

Allium sichuanense R.Kr.Singh, *nom. nov.*

≡ *Allium stoloniferum* D.F.Xie, R.Y.Cheng & X.J.He, Phytotaxa 711(2): 149. 2025, *nom. illeg., non* Ownbey & T.D.Jacobsen, Brittonia 31(3): 413. 1979.

Holotype: China, Sichuan Province, Pingwu County, 2960 m, 22 August 2024, D.-F. Xie 20240822-1 (SZAS001); isotypes (SZAS002–SZAS004).

Distribution: Endemic to Sichuan Province, China.

Etymology: Named after the Sichuan Province of China.

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